

**INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE IN
DENTISTRY 2022 NOVI SAD**

**PROCEEDINGS
OF THE INTERNATIONAL
SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE IN
DENTISTRY 2022 NOVI SAD**

**2nd of April 2022 :
Therapeutic and diagnostic principles in dental medicine I**

**3rd of April 2022 :
Therapeutic and diagnostic principles in dental medicine II**

CIP - Каталогizacija u publikaciji
Biblioteke Maticе српске, Нови Сад

616.31(082)

The INTERNATIONAL Scientific Conference in Dentistry (6 ; 2022 ; Novi Sad)
Proceedings of The [6th] International Scientific Conference in Dentistry 2022, 2-3rd
April, Novi Sad [Elektronski izvor] / editor Milica Jeremić Knežević. - Novi Sad :
Dentistry Clinic of Vojvodina, 2022

Način pristupa (URL): <https://simpozijumklinika.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Proceedings-2022.pdf>. - Opis zasnovan na stanju na dan
16.5.2022. - Nasl. sa naslovnog ekrana. - Bibliografija uz svaki rad.

ISBN 978-86-80894-05-8

a) Стоматологија -- Зборници
COBISS.SR-ID 66205705

**Organization of this Conference was approved by the Scientific
Council of the Dentistry Clinic of Vojvodina**

Editor: Dr Milica Jeremić Knežević, professor

Publisher: Dentistry Clinic of Vojvodina

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REMOVAL OF MATERIAL FROM ROOT CANAL DURING ENDODONTIC RETREATMENT

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Abstract: *An important step during retreatment is complete removal of the existing filling material, to gain access in all parts of the canal system. The type of core and sealer obturation material, use of different solvents and the possibility to use hand instruments or a variety of machine-driven instruments can influence the amount of residual material on canal walls. These factors can decrease the time needed for retreatment, however not necessarily have the same effect on the cleanliness of the canal walls. Methods and instruments that provide the most optimal results during retreatment procedures will be reviewed.*

Key words: *Endodontic retreatment, Material removal, Rotary instruments, Solvents*

Introduction

Nonsurgical endodontic retreatment is a procedure performed in a tooth that has already received a previous attempt of treatment and should be considered as the first choice of treatment whenever possible [1,2]. Orthograde endodontic retreatment involves removing the existing filling material with additional cleaning, disinfection and final obturation of the canal. An important step during retreatment is complete removal of the existing filling material, to gain access in all parts of the canal system. Removal as much material possible, followed by reinstrumentation and enlargement of the root canal provides better removal of necrotic tissues and microorganisms that may be responsible for the persistent periapical inflammation. However, complete root canal cleaning is almost impossible, regardless of the technique used for root canal preparation [3]. Also an important problem that should be addressed during retreatment is the apical extrusion of debris, root canal filling materials, dentin, microorganisms and irrigants through the apical foramen, regardless of the technique, instrument or material used [4]. This can cause periapical inflammation, flare-up and disruption of the healing process, that can be associated with the increasing amount of extruded debris [5]. There are a lot of studies in the literature that investigated retreatment and approached this issue from different perspectives.

Discussion

Different materials -generally a solid core material with an endodontic sealer-are usually used for root canal system obturation. Gutta-percha is the most commonly used core material for this purpose due to its stability and ability to be compacted [6]. Providing an adequate seal with gutta-percha is difficult due to the absence of bonding to root canal dentine and endodontic sealer. As an alternative, a synthetic polymer-based material, Resilon (Resilon Research LLC, Madison, WI), that shows thermoplastic ability similar to gutta-percha, has been introduced for use with methacrylate-based sealer to enable monoblock formation and to improve the bond to the root canal dentine. A polycaprolactone thermoplastic material with bioactive glass, bismuth, and barium salts as fillers has handling properties similar to gutta-percha. The material induces a chemical interaction that leads to the formation of a single resin block, which adheres to the root canal walls [7]. Some studies that evaluated the remaining filling material concluded that there was less material observed in teeth obturated with Resilon compared to gutta-percha and sealer. The study by Cunha et al. showed that Resilon/Real Seal system was removed in greater quantities from the canal walls compared with the [gutta-percha](#) cones and the [AH Plus](#) sealer [7]. However other studies showed no significant differences between different materials [8–10]. Also, some studies were conducted in order to test

whether the removal of Resilon material is harder, regarding the deeper penetration [11] and formation of monoblock inside the dentinal tubules and therefore measured the time needed for retreatment [12].

There are many different techniques for removal of root canal filling material: use of hand or rotary instruments, ultrasonics or heat-carrying instruments or a combination of these techniques. Rotary nickel-titanium (Ni-Ti) systems are preferred in endodontic retreatment because of their safety, efficiency and speed [13,14]. In order to improve the retreatment procedure, there are specially designed Ni-Ti instruments for the removal procedure itself, such as D-Race System (FKG Dentaire) and ProTaper Retreatment System (Dentsply, Maillefer, Switzerland) [10]. These systems are manufactured in a way to provide better efficiency but also safety during the removal procedure. Also, conventional Ni-Ti instruments that are produced for primary root canal preparation, could be used for the cause of material removal. However, the design of these instruments can be unfavorable and result in instrument separation or transportation of the canal. In studies conducted, instruments specially designed for retreatment were more efficient also in the amount of filling debris removed, compared to conventional rotary instruments. The use of machine-driven instrumentation is expected to be more efficient and time-saving compared to hand instruments. Also, the rotary instrumentation is proved to be safer compared to hand instruments concerning the amount of apically extruded debris [15].

Beside the rotary action, instruments that work with reciprocating action such as Reciproc (VDW, Munich, Germany) and single-file Ni-Ti system, such as OneShape (Micro-Mega, Cedex, France), that use only one file to prepare the entire canal, can also be used for retreatment. However the reciprocating instrument showed to produce more debris and extrusion compared to the rotary systems. The authors concluded that the advantage of the single-file system could be in regard to the working time needed for material removal [16].

The type of core and sealer obturation material and the use of different solvents during material removal can also influence the amount of residual material on canal walls. In clinical practice, different organic solvents, such as chloroform and xylol, have been used as auxiliaries to aid dissolving/softening during the removal of filling material [17]. Unlike chloroform, xylol is not considered a carcinogen and has superior solvency capacity than orange oil and eucalyptol [18,19]. Also, the use of solvents can facilitate the penetration of the instrument inside the filling material and aid the action of instruments, therefore decreasing the possibility for diversion and perforations [19,20]. However, the use of solvents alters the physical and chemical characteristics of the filling material and can reduce the effectiveness of the instrumentation [21]. The gutta-percha softened by the solvent action can result in forming a thin film that adheres to the surface of the root canal wall, which is more difficult to remove, even if enlargement of the canal is done by re-instrumentation [21,22]. In a study that investigated different solvents, the authors concluded that the use of a solvent specific to the sealer during retreatment decreased the amount of apically extruded debris [23].

As all the studies show, the materials from the root canal cannot be removed completely and remnants in different amount are always present on the canal walls, especially in the apical root third. The apical third of the root canal is the most complicated area in terms of complete smear layer and filling debris removal, regardless the type of filling materials [10] and instruments or other method used, during retreatment. Also, this finding shows that the absence of filling materials on the instruments, in the irrigating solution and the smoothness of root canal walls are not a valid criteria to demonstrate complete removal of filling material from the canal walls [24]. Rodig et al. [14] reported the need to complement biomechanical preparation with instruments of larger caliber. Studies [25,26] have demonstrated that the enlargement of the root canal reduces the amount of remaining filling material and provides enough space for the hydraulic effect of the irrigating solution to be efficient, while flushing out the debris [2]. Additional instrumentation can be done after initial material removal in order to improve the cleanliness of dentinal walls [27]. However apical instrumentation with No. 40 instrument is probably insufficient for the complete removal of the filling debris plugs present in all dentinal tubules [10]. The implementation of additional methods and aiding factors can decrease the time needed for retreatment, but not necessarily have the same effect on the cleanliness of the canal walls.

Conclusion

Obturation materials from the root canal cannot be removed completely and remnants in different amount are always present on the canal walls, especially in the apical root third. Implementation of different instruments, additional procedures, solvents and irrigation protocols can aid the removal of remaining material and improve canal cleanliness. However, these factors should be considered also in regard to the type of material and sealant to be removed and their extrusion through the apex. Approaches that provide the most optimal results in terms of canal cleanliness and effectiveness of the retreatment procedure should be employed in each individual retreatment case.

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